

Conference Abstract

Cryptic Diversity and Taxonomic Ambiguities in *Carassius carassius* from Czech Wetlands: Implications for Conservation

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Abstract

The crucian carp (*Carassius carassius*) is a native freshwater fish and an important indicator of wetland ecosystem health across Central Europe. However, its populations are increasingly threatened by habitat degradation and hybridization with non-native congeners. In this study, we present a mitochondrial cytochrome b (cytb) dataset from *C. carassius* populations sampled across various tributaries of the Danube and Elbe River basins in Czechia to evaluate genetic diversity and taxonomic clarity within the *Carassius* genus complex. Our preliminary results reveal multiple distinct mitochondrial haplotypes within nominal *C. carassius*, highlighting the presence of cryptic genetic diversity. These findings underscore the urgent need for integrative taxonomic approaches to support accurate species identification and conservation management. We advocate for the use of molecular tools in conservation monitoring programs to safeguard the genetic integrity of native *C. carassius* populations in vulnerable wetland habitats.

Keywords

Crucian carp, Integrative taxonomy, Genetic structure, Native fish populations

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.